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РАЗБИВАЛАСЬ ВСЯ ЛОГИКА, ВСЯ ФИЛОСОФИЯ, ВСЯ НАУКА.*

ЭРИХ МАРИЯ РЕМАРК

**НАУЧНО-ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ «ФИЗИКИ
РЕЗОНАНСНЫХ ЯДЕРНЫХ РЕАКЦИЙ» ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ НАУЧНЫМ
УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕМ, ОСУЩЕСТВЛЯЮЩИМ
ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ, ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ В
ОБЛАСТИ НАУКИ, ТЕХНИКИ, КУЛЬТУРЫ И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЯ.**

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SYNTHESIS OF GRAPHENE FROM GRAPHITE FOR THE PURPOSE OF OBTAINING CARBON NANOTUBES

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Abstract. This paper aims to synthesize carbon nanotubes using chemical methods under laboratory conditions, which are rarely discussed in the literature, based on the possibilities of obtaining graphene from graphite and the effective study of their chemical processes. In this process, graphene was chemically treated with nitric and sulfuric acids, potassium chlorate, and water as a solvent. It was also heated in a magnetic stirrer at a constant temperature for a specific period. The resulting sample was washed several times with distilled water to remove acids and solvents. Modern equipment and physicochemical methods, such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and infrared spectroscopy (IR), were used to analyze the initial reagents used in the experiment and the obtained product samples.

Keywords: graphene, graphite, carbon nanotube, scanning electron microscope (SEM) and infrared spectroscopy (IR), nitric and sulfuric acids, potassium permanganate, distilled water

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the territory of Uzbekistan stands out from other regions due to its abundance of chemical elements. This potential provides great opportunities for comprehensive development of the country's economy. We are faced with tasks of advancing science, extracting substances found in nature in various compound forms, and discovering new effective methods and technologies for producing environmentally safe products. For this reason, the education system of chemical sciences in our country is being given broad opportunities for the development of science.

Graphite, a chemical substance, is widely used in various social fields. Specifically, let's analytically examine the chemical properties and significance of graphene, which is a product of its oxidation. Graphene (Russian: графен, English: graphene) is a two-dimensional material with a thickness of one atom, consisting of carbon (C) atoms arranged in a hexagonal crystal lattice structure resembling a «honeycomb.» The graphite used for pencils is actually composed of many layers of graphene. Graphene was first synthesized in laboratory conditions in 2004 by a group of scientists at the University of Manchester (England) led by Andre Geim and Konstantin Novoselov, and in 2010 they were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics for this discovery. Graphene is not only the thinnest material in the world but also a very unusual material in terms of its physical properties: firstly, the strength of graphene compounds with some metals surpasses that of steel and diamond; secondly, its electrical, thermal, and light conductivity are extremely high. If metals (Al, Cu, Au, Ag, etc.) are bonded to it, these properties can increase hundredfold (it has been proven to be 200 times stronger than steel).

Currently, other physical, chemical, and biological properties of graphene are being intensively studied by scientists worldwide. Additionally, the discoveries of Uzbek scientists in collaboration with German scientists are aimed at controlling the conductivity of graphene nanoribbons using laser light. It has been theoretically proven that carbon nanotubes derived from graphene provide a wide range of opportunities for the country's economy. For instance, its use offers extensive possibilities in medicine, the production of environmentally friendly products, the creation of cost-effective products, the military sector, the development of modern tools in the field of technological activities, and other areas.

Extensive research is being conducted worldwide in the field of graphene. Notably, Russian scientist Mikhail Katznelson was awarded the Spinoza Prize in 2013 for developing the fundamental concept of graphene. This prize, which provides €2.5 million annually for new research, is often referred to as the

Dutch «Nobel Prize» among the scientific community. Graphene is considered a flat allotropic modification of c

The possibilities of using graphene in socio-economic life include:

– Graphite, a common and relatively inexpensive raw material, ensures economic efficiency in the production of graphene;

– The obtained graphene compounds possess unique properties such as high mechanical strength, electrical conductivity, and thermal conductivity;

– Graphene is currently used in cutting-edge fields, particularly in the production of nanoelectronics, batteries, solar cells, biosensors, and composite materials;

– Graphene oxide stands out from other substances due to its easy modification, making it adaptable for special purposes;

– Graphene oxide is highly soluble in water, which makes it convenient for creating mixtures and coating materials (for example, it is widely used in pharmaceuticals);

– the use of graphene in environmentally friendly technologies contributes to ensuring environmental sustainability. Especially in today's world, deterioration of the atmosphere is considered very effective in cases of water pollution. The discovery of new chemical and physical properties of graphene opens the way for the creation of mod

Synthesis. The process of obtaining carbon nanotubes from graphite is carried out using the Hummers method, but modified. Sulfuric acid, nitric acid, and potassium permanganate oxidize graphite to form graphite oxide. This process consists of the following steps:

A mixture of sulfuric acid (50 ml) and nitric acid (25 ml) is mixed with graphite (5 g).

2. Adding potassium permanganate (25 g) creates an oxidizing environment. In this process, graphite oxide is formed, and this reaction can be carried out under room conditions (70° C).

The resulting graphene is washed from the acid with distilled water.

Figure 1. Reaction of graphene extraction from graphite.

Figure 2. The reaction reagent is graphite.

The image of graphene, a reaction product, on a «SEM» (scanning electron microscope) is as follows:

(Figure 3)

Elemental analysis of the reagent obtained in SEM

Display name	Standard data	Quantification method	Result Type
Spc_004	Standardless	ZAF	Metal

Element	Line	Mass%	Atom%
C	K	84.99±0.08	89.45±0.09
O	K	12.94±0.11	10.23±0.09
Al	K	0.15±0.01	0.07±0.00
Si	K	0.08±0.00	0.03±0.00
S	K	0.21±0.01	0.08±0.00
K	K	0.14±0.01	0.05±0.00
Pt	M	1.49±0.02	0.10±0.00
Total		100.00	100.00
Spc_004			Fitting ratio 0.0071

Figure 4.

Elemental analysis of the SEM product:

Display name	Standard data	Quantification method	Result Type
Spc_013	Standardless	ZAF	Metal

Element	Line	Mass%	Atom%
C	K	67.74±1.14	75.48±1.27
O	K	26.49±1.57	22.16±1.31
Si	K	0.45±0.09	0.21±0.04
S	K	3.45±0.21	1.44±0.09
Cl	K	1.87±0.16	0.70±0.06
Total		100.00	100.00
Spc_013			Fitting ratio 0.0912

(Fig. 5)

Conclusion

The method of obtaining graphene by oxidizing graphite is an important stage in the production of high-quality graphene materials and lays the foundation for many innovative projects in the field of science and technology.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. https://azkurs.org/pars_docs/refs/128/127149/127149.pdf
2. Babajanov, D. et al. (2014). Particle Transport in Graphene Nanoribbon Driven by Ultrashort Pulses. *European Physical Journal B*. DOI 10.1140/epjb/e2014-50610-6
3. Bi, Jingxuan, et al. «On the road to the frontiers of lithium-ion batteries: a review and outlook of graphene anodes.» *Advanced Materials* 35.16 (2023): 2210734.
4. Saeed, Maryam, et al. «Chemical vapour deposition of graphene — Synthesis, characterisation, and applications: A review.» *Molecules* 25.17 (2020): 3856.
5. Wang, Jia-bin, et al. «A review of graphene synthesis at low temperatures by CVD methods.» *New Carbon Materials* 35.3 (2020): 193—208.

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